

HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF "ABDULLANOMA" ("SHARAFNAMAI SHAHIY").

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Abstract: *This article provides information about the life and works of the 16th century historian Hafiz Tanish Bukhari. In particular, the work "Abdullanoma", a unique source written by Hafiz Tanish Bukhari, and its historical significance are highlighted.*

Keywords: *Bukhara khanate, Shaibanis, Abdullah Khan II, Hafiz Tanish Bukhari, "Abdullanoma", unique source, "Sharafnomayi Shahi", prose, rhyme, sheikhs of Joybor, I.I. Umniyakov.*

The human factor is the basis of society. The development of the masses is related to the mental development of a person. As the number of educated people increases in the society, there will be development and progress. Science is such a factor that people who follow it will never be humiliated. History is such a science that it is considered the father of all sciences. One of the differences of history from other sciences is that it awakens education, drawing conclusions, pride, self-awareness, and love for the Motherland. It is through this science of history that we can find out all the factors that cause the decline, development, war, and peace of society. Yesterday is also history, we will try not to make the same mistakes we made yesterday. Everything that remains of us continues to create our history, for better or for worse. The ancestors who lived before us created our beautiful history with their perseverance, hard work and courage. There are periods in the past that we don't know about, and we have to rely on material and written sources to bring them to our eyes. The Shaibanis (1500-1601), who came to power after the great Timurid state, centralized the scattered country and ensured peace. After Muhammad Shaybani Khan, Abdullah Khan II was the main representative of

Shaybani who kept the integrity of the state and centralized it. Hafiz Tanish Bukhari's work "Abdullahnama" (Sharafnamai Shahi) which helps to illuminate the history of this period is one of the valuable sources.

We have not received enough information about Hafiz Tanish Bukhari. He was one of the mature poets of his time. He is known by the nicknames "Nakhli" and "Kiromi". Hafiz Tanish Bukhari was born in 1540 in Bukhara. His father lived in Bukhara during the time of Maulana Mir Muhammad Ubaidullah Khan (1533-1539) and was one of the khan's close relatives. He went to Kashgar at the beginning of 1550 and died there about two years later [1, - B. 216.] Hafiz Tanish Bukhari studied in Bukhara madrasas. He was one of the most accomplished scholars of Abdullah Khan's court and in 1584, he started writing the work "Abdullanoma" with the interpretation of Qulbobo Ko'kaldosh, a close friend of Abdullah Khan II, and served as the palace historian [2, - B. 213.]. According to information, Hafiz Tanish Bukhari was 36 years old when he started writing the work.

Hafiz Tanish Bukhari is known for his royal work - "Abdullanoma" ("Sharafnomai shahi"). The work is dedicated to Shaybani ruler Abdulla Khan II and was written in Persian language in Bukhara in 1584-1588.

According to the author's plan, the work will consist of an introduction, 2 parts (article) and a conclusion. In the preface, as usual, praise to the supreme ruler, the reasons for writing the work, brief information about Abdullah's ancestors, Turko-Mongol tribes that have lived in Central Asia since ancient times, Genghis Khan and his descendants are given. In the first article, the events that may happen in Central Asian Kazakhstan and neighboring foreign countries after 1583. In the introduction, the qualities of Abdullah Khan are given about the sheikhs, scholars, poets, ministers and emirs who were contemporaries with him, as well as the buildings built during Abdullah Khan's time. But in the process of writing the work, the plan changed, the first and second articles were added. The conclusion was left unfinished due to the untimely death of the author [3, - B. 239.].

The work is written in the form of rhymed prose, the language and form are extremely heavy. The work is rich in similes and metaphors. The book describes the

socio-political history of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, and Iran in the 15th century. In addition, information about cultural, political, trade-diplomatic relations between nations is also provided. Mutrubi, one of his contemporaries, says that Hafiz Tanish Bukhari finished his work in the 80s of the 16th century.

From the point of view of the period in which the work was written, science has progressed, peace and political stability have been achieved, and in the fight for the throne, Iskandar Khan's son Abdulla Khan II (1557-1598) has the upper hand in Shaybaniza. During the reign of Abdullah Khan II in Movoraunnahr, he founded a strong centralized state. Detailed information about this is given in "Abdullanoma" [4, - B.21.].

The work provides detailed information about religious scholars who played a major role in the social and political life of that time. The great figures of religion were such persons who had an important place in the internal and external life of the state. They even influenced the khans. The respect for them was so strong that the princes who were born were taken to them to be named and blessed. For example, in the play, when Abdullah Khan II was born, Sultan Iskandar took him to Khoja Kasani (Makhdumi A'zam), an accomplished religious scholar of his time, to give him a name. Khoja Kosani named the prince Abdullah Khan [5, - B. 157.]. In addition, detailed information was given about the sheikhs of Dzhoybor, who had a great political position in the 16th and 17th centuries, who helped Abdullah Khan enter the political arena and fight for the throne. The sheikhs of Dzhoybor are descendants of Imam Ali and spread religion from Mecca and Medina to Nishapur and then to Bukhara. One of them was Abu Bakr Sa'd Yemeni sheikhul-Islam. His grandson Muhammad Islam also had great influence and was the elder of Abdullah Khan [6, - B. 135 -136]. The reason why the sheikhs of Dzhoybor got this name was when the grandfather of Muhammad Islam, Khwaja Muhammad Yahya, moved to Dzhoybor in Bukhara, they were called Dzhoybor sheikhs. We can see in the work that their property and state were very incalculable: "The quick calculators of the seven climates cannot calculate even one hundredth of their property" [7, - B. 147.]. From this we can see that the sheikhs of Dzhoybor occupied a great place in political

and economic life. Muhammad Islam built a house, a mosque and a madrasa dedicated to his grandfather Abu Bakr Sa'd, and turned its surroundings into a garden. Abu Bakr builds a garden for Abdullah Khan in front of Sa'd's tomb [8, - B. 279-281.]. They also contributed to the prosperity of the country.

Also, the work covers in detail the political and military campaigns of Abdullah Khan II, the struggle for the throne, the reforms he carried out, and the diplomatic relations. The work has been attracting the attention of Oriental scholars for several centuries. Orientalist I.I. Umniyakov studied 17 copies of the work in depth and says that the work occupies an important place in the study of the history of Central Asia in the 16th century. Sadiq Mirzayev, a well-known Uzbek orientalist, made a great contribution to the translation of the work into Uzbek. The scientist worked on the work for ten years and finished it in 1951 [9, - B. 368.]. From this we can conclude that the book is valuable about the political, economic, trade, diplomatic relations of the 16th century, about the khans and the activities of Abdullah Khan II. The role of such sources is invaluable in illuminating the glorious history of our country, in awakening the feeling of love for the Motherland, and in understanding our identity.

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